

GEANT4 on Large Intel Xeon Phi Clusters: Service Implementation and Performance

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Abstract

The fast and precise simulation of particle interactions with matter is an important task for several scientific areas, ranging from fundamental science (high-energy physics experiments, astrophysics and astroparticle physics, nuclear investigations) through applied science (radiation protection, space science), to biology and medicine (DNA investigations, hadron therapy, medical physics and medical imaging) and education. The basic software in all these fields is Geant4 (GEometry ANd Tracking) – a platform for simulation of the passage of particles through matter [1]. Along the way towards enabling the execution of Geant4 based simulations on HPC architectures with large clusters of Intel Xeon Phi co-processors as a general service, we study the performance of this software suit on the supercomputer system Avitohol@BAS, commenting on the pitfalls in the installation and compilation process. Some practical scripts are collected in the supplementary material shown in the appendix.

INTRODUCTION

GEANT4 [1] is a software toolkit for simulation of the interactions of particles with matter. It exploits the object-oriented technology to achieve transparency of the physics implementation, as well as openness to extension and evolution. GEANT4 encompasses a wide set of tools for all the domains of detector simulation, including geometry modelling, detector response, run and event management, tracking, visualization and user interface. An abundant set of physics processes handles the diverse interactions of particles with matter across a wide energy range, as required by GEANT4 multi-disciplinary nature. The GEANT4 source code, libraries and user documentation are freely available [2-4].

GEANT4 is the successor of the FORTRAN-based GEANT series of software toolkits [5], which dates back to 1978. GEANT4 is the first version developed using object oriented technology and is implemented in C++. GEANT4 can be used as a stand-alone tool and linked as a library. For example, in applications like CMSSW [6] (high-energy physics) and GATE [7] (medical physics), GEANT4 is accessed through a complex framework.

The HPC approach used is based on GRID technology. The largest research facilities in HEP (high-energy physics) use the Worldwide LHC Computing Grid (WLCG) infrastructure to perform such simulations. In this approach, different computers simulate different events. The events are fully independent, so no data transfer between different computers is needed. The problems along this way are two-fold:

- With the increasing data volumes, the resources become more and more insufficient, even with structures like WLCG.
- New architectures like those involving large number of Intel Xeon Phi accelerators are not used efficiently by the largest HPC community worldwide.

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Our long-term goal is to provide a service, allowing for the execution of GEANT4 based simulations on platforms with multiple Intel Xeon Phi co-processors and enabling such HPC infrastructure to be used by large-scale scientific instruments (like the LHC experiments), but also by hadron therapy facilities and other interested parties.

REQUIREMENTS

Simulations for HEP experiments

As a representative example of the modern experiments in the field of HEP we consider the experiments at the CERN LHC collider. Four detector complexes (ATLAS, CMS, LHCb and ALICE) are installed on LHC. Experiments have to disentangle the real physical phenomena from detector related effects, i.e. measurements from systematic effects. The way for doing this is creating sufficient amount of synthetic data through simulations of particle collisions and interactions with the detector. This synthetic data has the same format as the real experimental data, which makes it possible to run data analysis algorithms alternatively on simulated or real events. The synthetic data has to be transferred and stored on LHC Tier-0 or Tier-1 to allow LHC collaborations using it in parallel with the real data.

Figure 1. Simulation of 1 TeV positive muon, hitting a fixed-target experimental setup, including lead target disk and five detector disks, with a different number of simulated events: 1 (left), 10 (middle) and 100 (right). The geometry of the setup is visible only on the first plot. On the other plots the experimental setup is not visible due to the high number of primary and secondary particle tracks.

The particles are tracked through user defined geometry and simulations can be performed within different physical models. The simulation is based on Monte Carlo computations. A typical simulation is presented in Fig. 1.

At present, the standard procedure to speed-up GEANT4 simulations is running them on PC-farms or on the Grid. GPU usage is not employed due to the necessity for severe modifications of the code. For Intel Xeon Phi platform, there is no need for doing so in native mode. This is also the mode recommended by the developers [8]. The workflow is shown in Fig. 2. The step, involving GEANT4 computations, is the most challenging in terms of computational resources and storage space. The designed service “GEANT4 on MIC” aims at relaxing this bottleneck by opening it for hybrid architectures with Intel Xeon Phi co-processors.

Simulations for hadron-therapy facilities

GEANT4 simulations are used for patient treatment planning, treatment verification and validation and hadron-therapy-related research. The input to the simulation is the anatomical description of the patient, which vary for different patients and even for the same patient at different stages of the treatment. The geometrical description of beam setup and the gantry, which are the same for a given facility and do not change much in the time, is also an input to the simulation. The output of the simulation is a map of the radiation dose and other essential parameters.

Usually the simulation is performed on dedicated computing resources, installed locally in the hadron therapy facilities. The service developed for the HEP case is in principle suitable also for the hadron therapy centres, because the procedure is similar to the HEP case, except for the smaller data volume. The regulations for dealing with personal data – in particular, medical data – impose strict requirements on the security of the data and data transfer.

In both cases, no persistent storage is foreseen, because the product of the service (output of the simulation) is transferred to the users. Thus, only temporary storage is required.

Figure 2. A typical HEP workflow (in blue). The proposed service (GEANT4 simulation on MIC, marked in red) should gradually replace the existing GEANT4 simulation step (in blue).

The workflow is very similar to the HEP case, except for some additional automatic encryption/decryption procedures of the transferred data for personal data protection purposes.

SERVICE DESIGN

Storage and data transfer

The configuration files which setup GEANT4 simulations are very small and different files are needed for different simulations. The geometrical description of the experimental setup can be large enough but does not change from simulation to simulation. The volume of the output of the simulation is the real challenge in terms of storage and data transfer.

The specifics of input and output data for GEANT4 simulations defines the service architecture (Fig. 3).

The service requires three different types of storage:

- i) Small temporary storage for upload of user configuration files to set up the MC simulation;
- ii) Small persistent storage for upload of the geometrical description, numerical constants and other input data;
- iii) Large short-term temporary storage for the simulation output; this output has to be downloaded by the users to the respective permanent storage (e.g. LCG Tier-1 or Tier-2 in the HEP case or data server in case of hadron therapy facility).

The storages can be organized as folders in an AFS [9] file system (securely and easily accessed by the clients) or could be organized as local folders on the front-end with SFTP access or even using the XROOTD [10]. The huge volume of the simulation output is challenging also in terms of data transfer (see [11]). The best solution is to use the GEANT network [12] to ensure good and reliable connectivity between the service provider and the clients. Clients connect to the service via the GEANT network and after authentication and administrative checks (for user quota, etc.) are logged in into the user interface, where they have access to the above-mentioned storages and to the front-end node of the HPC system. The simulation is started from the front-end node.

Figure 3. Service architecture.

TEST ARCHITECTURE

A pilot implementation of the service “GEANT4 on MIC” was realized on the Sofia HPC system Avitohol@BAS [13], with 300 CPU Intel Xeon E5-2650v2, 300 co-processors Intel Xeon Phi 7120P, 9.6 TB memory and LINPACK performance of 264.2 TFlop/s. The operating system is Red Hat Enterprise Linux release 6.7. The co-processors run MPSS version 3.6. The GEANT package requires a number of additional libraries and packages being configured and installed in a specific way in advance. File-transfer options will be discussed elsewhere, here we shall focus on the installation, compilation and performance of GEANT4 on this particular heterogeneous system.

GEANT4 INSTALLATION

The multithread enabled GEANT4.10.00.p04 library has been installed on Avitohol supercomputer as well as the CMAKE-3.3.2 utility needed to set up and compile user code linked to the GEANT4. Several test programs have been compiled and run successfully in multithread version in order to test and validate the correctness of the installation.

The GEANT4 pre-requisites are the following:

- GEANT4 version 10.0 patch-04,
- Intel C/C++ version 16.X or higher. We have used ICC and ICPP version 16.0.2 (compatible with gcc version 4.4.7),
- Intel MPSS (Manycore Platform Support Stack) version 3.4,
- CMake version 3.3 or higher,
- C++ Compiler and Standard Library supporting the C++11 standard,
- Linux: GNU Compiler Collection 4.8.2 or higher.

We refer to the corresponding section of the Best Practice Guide Intel Xeon Phi v2.0 [14] for performing the following steps:

- GEANT4 configuration and installation,
- GEANT4 cross compilation as a native Xeon Phi application,
- GEANT4 user code compilation and execution on CPU,
- GEANT4 user code compilation and execution on Xeon Phi in native mode.

In the Appendix, some useful scripts are given as supplementary material.

The new version of the suite – GEANTV, which aims for complete parallelization and which is still under development – needs many specific packages to be pre-installed, most of them to be compiled and installed from scratch. The installation order is determined by the package dependencies and the compilation options have to be explicitly specified. The default system compiler on Red Hat Enterprise Linux release 6.7 is not sufficient to compile GEANTV and even the GNU compiler should be compiled from scratch, together with some libraries needed by the compiler. Any version above 4.8.0 should be sufficient. We have tested that version 4.8.5 works. Performance of GEANTV will be studied separately.

Prior to GEANTV compilation, the following packages have to be properly configured and installed:

- ROOT6 (<https://root.cern.ch/>)
- Vc (<https://github.com/VcDevel/Vc>)
- VecGeom (<https://gitlab.cern.ch/VcGeom/VcGeom>)
- Pythia8 (<http://home.thep.lu.se/~torbjorn/Pythia.html>)
- HepMC3 (<https://hepmc.web.cern.ch/hepmc/>)
- Xerces-c (<http://xerces.apache.org/xerces-c/>)
- GEANT4 (<https://geant4.web.cern.ch/geant4/>)

PERFORMANCE ANALYSIS

Different numbers of events (1000, 10 000, 100 000 and 1 000 000) have been simulated using 1, 8 and 10 threads on the CPU and 1, 60 and 244 threads on the co-processor. In Fig. 4, Fig. 5 the execution time as a function of the number of threads for different event and thread numbers is shown.

Speedup and performance for a simple fixed target experiment

A beam of positive muons with energy of 1 TeV has been sent to a fixed lead target and the primary and secondary particles has been traced through an experimental setup containing five detector disks. The lead target is 5 cm thick, while the detectors are 20 cm thick ionization chambers filled with Xenon. The distance between the center of the target and the first chamber is 80 cm. The distance between centres of neighbouring chambers is also 80 cm. The bulk space is filled with air. The results are shown in Fig. 4.

Fig. 4. Execution time vs. number of threads for 1 000 events (left) and 10000 events (right) on the Intel Xeon CPUs.

The configuration file used is:

```
/tracking/verbose 0
/control/cout/useBuffer true
/control/cout/ignoreThreadsExcept 0
# mu+ 1TeV
/gun/energy 1 TeV
/gun/particle mu+
/run/beamOn 1000000
Exit
```

Comparison between the execution on the CPU and on the co-processor alone

Test-code compilation for both cases is as follows:

```
source /opt/soft/geant4/mic/non-
mic/scripts/geant4_compilers_setup_nonmic.sh
mkdir ~/test_cpu
cd ~/test_cpu
mkdir B2a
cd B2a
cmake -DCMAKE_LINKER=${LD} -DCMAKE_AR=${AR} -
DCMAKE_TOOLCHAIN_FILE=/opt/soft/geant4/mic/non-mic/geant4.10.00.p04//mic-
toolchain-file.cmake -DGeant4_DIR=/opt/soft/geant4/mic/non-
mic/geant4.10.00.p04/geant4.10.00.p04-build/
/opt/soft/geant4/mic/non-
mic/geant4.10.00.p04/geant4.10.00.p04/examples/basic/B2/B2a/
make -j 40
```


Figure 5. Execution time vs. number of events for different number of threads.

```
source /opt/soft/geant4/mic/non-
mic/scripts/geant4_compilers_setup_nonmic.sh
mkdir ~/test_mic
cd ~/test_mic
mkdir B2a
cd B2a
cmake -DCMAKE_LINKER=${LD} -DCMAKE_AR=${AR} -
DCMAKE_TOOLCHAIN_FILE=/opt/soft/geant4/mic/geant4.10.00.p04/mic-toolchain-
file.cmake -
DGeant4_DIR=/opt/soft/geant4/mic/geant4.10.00.p04/geant4.10.00.p04-build/
/opt/soft/geant4/mic/geant4.10.00.p04/geant4.10.00.p04/examples/basic/B2/B2
a/
make -j 40
```

The number of the threads in the tests is chosen to be 1, 8, and 10 for the CPU and 1, 60, and 244 for the co-processor. Comparing one thread on the CPU to one on the co-processor aims to reveal the intrinsic performance of the corresponding architectures. 8 corresponds to the number of physical cores of the CPU at the test architecture, while 244 corresponds to the maximal number of threads for the co-processor. We have performed also tests with 60 threads on the co-processor, corresponding to 1 thread per physical core, leaving one physical core to cope with system functions. In all these cases the CPU outperforms the co-processor for small number of simulated events, but for high number of simulated events the performances of the selected configurations are comparable.

The results are presented in Fig. 5. The time per event for different number of threads on the CPU and on the co-processor is given in the Tables below and shown in Fig. 6.

Threads	1k events	10k events	100k events	1000k events
1	0,006	0,0052	0,000488	0,004858
8	0,003	0,0008	0,00068	0,000672
10	0,003	0,0008	0,00056	0,000539

Table 1. Time per event in [s] for the CPU.

Threads	1k events	10k events	100k events	1000k events
1	0,109	0,0895	0,09043	0,0448
60	0,072	0,0097	0,00251	0,001633
244	0,251	0,0283	0,0038	0,001101

Table 2. Time per event in [s] for Intel Xeon Phi.

It can be clearly seen that performing the simulation on the co-processor with the maximal number of threads becomes competitive with increasing the number of events.

Figure 6. Time per event in [s] (double log scale for Intel Xeon (left panel) and for Intel Xeon Phi (right panel)).

Finally, we consider an example with different particles – protons, though in the same experimental setup, and draw a parallel to the muon case studied so far. The important difference (in this context) is the way these particles interact with matter. Muons produce only a few secondary particles, while protons generate a whole shower.

Figure 7. Execution time vs. number of threads for different particles and 10000 events (left), and 128000 events (right) for Intel Xeon Phi.

The results presented in Fig. 7 confirm the expectations. For muons, the execution times reach a minimum at 32 threads and then increase again, while for protons we observe a rapid decrease up to 32 threads and only a minor decrease afterwards. Thus, in the muon case the benefits of the increased number of threads cannot compensate the increased setup time. For the larger number of events (Fig. 6, right panel), the muon curve has not yet reached a minimum.

Our results are qualitatively in very good agreement with the ones reported in [15, 16]. However, a direct quantitative comparison is not possible, because of the different benchmarks used in these three studies and the different hardware. Our study is performed using Intel Xeon Phi 7120P [17], while the results reported in [15,16] are obtained using Xeon Phi 5110P [18].

CONCLUSIONS

The results show an essential speedup with the number of threads for increasing number of simulated events in all tested configurations. The performance depends of the particular physical case. The benefits of multi-threading are evident for large number of particles, no matter if secondary or primary ones. The scaling behavior can be well understood in the context of the particle properties. Our recommendation to the users is to choose a high number of threads if the simulation produces a high number of secondary particles. For cases with a smaller number of secondary particles, a performance increase can be achieved in two ways:

- by finding the optimal number of threads and keeping to it for the given class of simulations,
- by performing the simulation with a sufficiently high number of primary particles (at least 1000) per thread.

Formally, the co-processor does not outperform the CPU, but for a large number of simulated events (which is the real case) the Xeon Phi performance is comparable with the CPU performance. It should be emphasized that porting an extremely large package like GEANT4 to a new architecture is usually far from trivial. Thus, this option is not considered by the developers for Nvidia CUDA as the code requires essential changes. On the contrary, the source code needs little or almost no changes in order to be compiled and executed on Intel Xeon Phi, which is a remarkable advantage, making it the only hybrid platform able to run GEANT4. Another remarks concerns the fact that GEANT4 is not optimized for parallel computations. The fully parallelized version of the suite, GEANTV, which is still under development, will expectedly provide an overall performance enhancement, including that on co-processors of the series Intel Xeon Phi. With the energy efficiency in mind, such heterogeneous architectures are a promising candidate for offloading to them part of these important and computationally expensive simulations.

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APPENDIX

GEANT4 user code compilation and execution on CPU

We recommend the following script to be used in order to facilitate the compilation of the user code and linking it to the GEANT4 library:

```
#!/bin/bash
#echo $0 usage: user_install_dir user_source_code_dir
echo usage: user_install_dir user_source_code_dir
#echo $# #arguments
if [ $# -ne 2 ]
    then echo "illegal number of parameters"
    exit
fi
echo $1 $2

/opt/intel/compilers_and_libraries_2016.2.181/linux/bin/iccvars.sh intel64
-arch intel64 -platform linux
export
CC=/opt/intel/compilers_and_libraries_2016.2.181/linux/bin/intel64/icc
export
CXX=/opt/intel/compilers_and_libraries_2016.2.181/linux/bin/intel64/icpc
export LD=/usr/linux-klom-4.7/bin/x86_64-klom-linux-ld
export AR=/usr/linux-klom-4.7/bin/x86_64-klom-linux-ar
export PATH=/opt/soft/geant4/mic/cmake-3.3.2/bin/:${PATH}
#export
LD_LIBRARY_PATH=$LD_LIBRARY_PATH:/opt/intel/compilers_and_libraries_2016.2.
181/linux/compiler/lib/intel64_lin
export
LD_LIBRARY_PATH=/opt/intel/compilers_and_libraries_2016.2.181/linux/compile
r/lib/intel64_lin
```

```
cd $1
```

```
cmake -DCMAKE_LINKER=${LD} -DCMAKE_AR=${AR} -  
DCMAKE_TOOLCHAIN_FILE=/opt/soft/geant4/mic/non-mic/geant4.10.00.p04/mic-  
toolchain-file.cmake -DGeant4_DIR=/opt/soft/geant4/mic/non-  
mic/geant4.10.00.p04/geant4.10.00.p04-build $2
```

where the content of mic-toolchain-file.cmake is listed in [9].

The compilation is performed by:

```
./compile_user_code.sh $USR_BUILD $USR_CODE
```

where the user code is in the directory pointed by the environment variable \$USR_CODE and the directory to build and store executable is pointed by \$USR_BUILD.

GEANT4 user code compilation and execution on Xeon Phi in native mode

We recommend the following script to facilitate the compilation of the user code and linking it to the GEANT4 library:

```
#!/bin/bash  
#echo $0 usage: user_install_dir user_source_code_dir  
echo usage: user_install_dir user_source_code_dir  
#echo $# #arguments  
if [ $# -ne 2 ]  
    then echo "illegal number of parameters"  
    exit  
fi  
  
/opt/intel/compilers_and_libraries_2016.2.181/linux/bin/iccvars.sh intel64  
-arch intel64 -platform linux  
export  
CC=/opt/intel/compilers_and_libraries_2016.2.181/linux/bin/intel64/icc  
export  
CXX=/opt/intel/compilers_and_libraries_2016.2.181/linux/bin/intel64/icpc  
export LD=/usr/linux-klom-4.7/bin/x86_64-klom-linux-ld  
export AR=/usr/linux-klom-4.7/bin/x86_64-klom-linux-ar  
export LDFLAGS=-mmic  
export CXXFLAGS=-mmic  
export CFLAGS=-mmic  
export PATH=/opt/soft/geant4/mic/cmake-3.3.2/bin/:${PATH}  
cd $1  
cmake -DCMAKE_LINKER=${LD} -DCMAKE_AR=${AR} -  
DCMAKE_TOOLCHAIN_FILE=/opt/soft/geant4/mic/geant4.10.00.p04/mic-toolchain-  
file.cmake -  
DGeant4_DIR=/opt/soft/geant4/mic/geant4.10.00.p04/geant4.10.00.p04-build $2
```

where the content of mic-toolchain-file.cmake is given in [6]. The compilation is straightforward:

```
./compile_user_code_mic.sh $USR_BUILD $USR_CODE
```

where the user code is in the directory pointed by the environment variable \$USR_CODE and the directory to build and store executable is pointed by \$USR_BUILD.

Running the code on Xeon Phi

Instead of explicitly logging in on the MIC co-processor the user could store the necessary commands for the setup of the environment variables as well as the executable command in a shells script (for example run.sh) and then launch the application in the following way:

```
ssh sl051-mic0 'run.sh'
```